

Milestone MS.3

Seed sampling (and re-sampling if needed) for the selected populations

Due date of milestone: 31.12.2024

Actual achievement date: 31.12.2024

Work package concerned: WP1 - CWR inventory and knowledge

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'Milestones' are control points in the action that help to chart progress. They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverables, allowing the next phase of the work to begin or be needed at intermediary points (go-no-go point).

A milestone, contrary to a deliverable, will not be submitted on the EU participant portal but some part of it will be used on the EU portal.

The core of this report (all sections except annexes) should be short (~1 page and a half). Details can be added as annexes.

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Project funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme.

Abstract

Seeds were sampled from the selected trees of the selected CWR populations according to the sampling design developed for this project in Task 1.2 and presented in MS2. From each mother tree, 20 to 30 healthy fruits were collected, and at least 20 healthy, mature seeds were extracted and kept separately at tree level. In total, 2,838 mother trees from wild species of *Malus*, *Pyrus*, and *Prunus* were sampled for leaves. However, due to varying climatic conditions and the year of each sampling site, seed samples were collected from 1,828 mother trees. **Seed collection could not be completed in some CWR populations this year, as not all trees bear fruits (the level of fructification and its quality was unknown when trees were selected in early spring).** Fruit re-sampling will continue next year in the relevant populations.

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1 Background

Previous milestone or previous work that allowed to achieve this one.

Milestone MS3 is part of WP1 that will:

- ✓ Perform a complete inventory and network mapping of public and private ex-situ CWR collections.
- ✓ Develop the sampling design and sample plant material from the in-situ CWR populations.
- ✓ Perform phenotyping of in-situ CWR populations and individuals
- ✓ Assess the leaf and root level micro-biodiversity associated to CWR populations through metabarcoding.
- ✓ Detail and monitor all the legal, technical and ethical procedures for germplasm sampling and use.

MS3 reports on the status of in-situ CWR seed collection and the related metadata achieved by Month 12 of the project. This report builds on the results obtained in MS2, from Month 6, when the design and protocol for in-situ plant material sampling was developed.

2 Work done and current status

Please, make a short description of the results or decisions taken for this milestone.

Each partner sampled seeds from the fruit trees within the CWR populations according to the sampling design developed for this project in Task 1.2 and presented in MS2. From each mother tree, depending on the level of potential fruit infestation and fructification, 20 to 30 healthy fruits were collected, and seeds were extracted. At least 20 healthy, mature seeds were extracted from the fruits of each mother tree and placed in individual small paper envelopes. Seeds were kept separately at tree level, i.e. each envelope containing seeds from only one tree. The same codes and labels used for the leaf samples were applied to each seed sample as well (first 3 letters of genus and 3 letters of species name, country, year, three first letters of site and number of sampled tree, i.e. pyrcom_fr24_lon_01; malsyl_ro24_tra_01; pruavi_gr24_tsa_02; pruweb_it_xxx_01).

The status of the fruit tree CWR seed sampling is summarized in Table 1 below. In total, 2,838 mother trees from wild species of *Malus*, *Pyrus*, and *Prunus* were sampled for leaves. However, due to varying climatic conditions and each sampling site, seed samples were collected from 1,828 mother trees for year 2024.

Table 1. Number of individual trees sampled for seeds and corresponding number of populations sampled per genus and species respectively.

<i>Taxon</i>	<i>Number of trees sampled for seeds</i>	<i>Number of populations</i>
<i>Malus</i>	201	31
<i>orientalis</i>	44	4
<i>sylvestris</i>	157	27
<i>Prunus</i>	1193	83
<i>avium</i>	318	23
<i>cerasifera</i>	256	17

<i>cocomilia</i>	167	9
<i>divaricata</i>	17	1
<i>dulcis</i>	6	1
<i>fenzliana</i>	40	2
<i>nairica</i>	17	1
<i>ramburi</i>	15	2
<i>tenella</i>	77	10
<i>webbii</i>	280	17
<i>Pyrus</i>	434	33
<i>caucasica</i>	14	1
<i>eleagrifolia</i>	19	1
<i>pyraster</i>	382	30
<i>salicifolia</i>	19	1
<i>Grand Total</i>	1828	147

3 Deviations or delays

3.1 Description/ reason (if applicable)

Seed collection could not be completed in some CWR populations this year, as not all trees bear fruits. It should be noted that the level of fructification and its quality was unknown when trees were selected in early spring. In fact, the need for re-sampling was foreseen, as it can be appreciated from the tittle of the Milestone.

3.2 Impact on other tasks (if applicable)

These seed samples will be used in T3.1 for multiplication and planting of the *ex-situ* wild core collections in the European network of genetic conservation orchards. We are not foreseeing so far problems for this task since we already collected fruits for a fair number of trees per populations (see table 1). However, some additional planting may be needed regarding the new seed collection in year 2025.

3.3 Corrective actions to be taken to come back to schedule (if applicable)

Fruit re-sampling will continue next year in the relevant populations.

4 Annexes

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 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101133964

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 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101133964

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 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101133964

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 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101133964